

FUNCTIONING OF IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS IN THE ENGLISH PRESS

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Abstract

This study is devoted to the study of the idiomatic expressions functioning in the texts of English press. These are the statements and expressions that enrich the language, enhancing its aesthetic features, filling it with a description of the world around us and our life. Phraseology and, closely related to it, the idioms of the English language have rather blurred boundaries. The opinions of linguists on the issue of the identity of the concepts of “phraseology” and “idiom” differ, in most cases, research papers that somehow intersect with the topic of our study do not contain a specific or unified description of definitions and classifications of idioms of the English language.

From the point of view of the classification of idiomatic expressions, their differentiation by individual types may present some difficulties, since in some scientific works linguists correlate idioms with phraseological units of the language, which affects the uniformity of their classifications. Thus, the structural classification of idioms and phraseological units is of the same type: idioms are distinguished by their structure into idioms – free phrases, idioms with a compositional or predicative structure, idioms with the character of interjection, idioms of a comparative nature, single-vertex structures: consisting of a significant word and one or more official parts of speech and verb-postpositive idioms.

The function of idiomatic expression in the text is similar to the function of phraseology, in connection with which we can talk about such types of idiomatic expressions as nominative and nominative-communicative idioms.

The scientific novelty of the work consists in an attempt to consider the English idiomatic expressions from the point of view of motivation and functioning.

Keywords: language studies, English, linguistics, idiom, phraseology, press

1 INTRODUCTION

There is no unambiguous solution to the problem of defining the concept of “idiom”. Although it has been used for quite a long time in the linguistic works and research of numerous researchers. Despite this, the

concept, namely its content and scope of meaning, still do not have a clear and unambiguous interpretation and are still the subject of various discussions.

There is a point of view that equates the concepts of “idiom” and “phraseology”. This opinion is shared by modern researchers of idioms and phraseology of the English language (Krysin, 2008). An idiom is a stable expression consisting of several components. Each of these components has its own direct meaning. The general meaning of the idiom is always different from these meanings. A huge variety of immutable structures that do not obey or violate either the rules of grammar or logic is a special feature of idioms.

Thus, it can be concluded that the idiom is essentially a phraseological unit, and it can be designated as a “phraseological fusion”.

Phraseological fusion, or idiom (from Greek “own, proper”) is a semantically indivisible turnover, the meaning of which is not deducible from the values of its constituent components: *to kick the bucket*– to die; *to rain cats and dogs* – to pour like a bucket (about rain); *to be all thumbs* – to be awkward, clumsy. The difference between phraseological fusions and combinations, unities is the impossibility of deducing the general meaning from these elements.

D’Arcais Giovanni B. Flores is of the opinion that most linguists interpret an idiom as “a phrasal unit whose meaning cannot be deduced from its syntactic components” (D’Arcais Giovanni, 1993, pp. 80-81). The linguist considers the following to be the main properties of idioms:

- cohesiveness and flexibility;
- lexical status of idioms and their representation in the mental lexicon;
- idiomatic analysis and syntactic separateness;
- uniqueness;
- transparency and blurriness.

A. Langlots considers idioms as complex language configurations. The researcher concluded that idiomatic constructions can be described as complex symbols with specific pragmatic, formal, semantic sociolinguistic characteristics (Langlots, 2006). The most characteristic features of idioms include stability, institutionalization, incompositionality and compatibility. At the same time, there is a coexistence of a wide and narrow scope of idiomatics.

2 METHODS

The empirical material of this study was 200 idiomatic expressions from British newspapers and magazines “New Statesman”, “Guardian”, “Daily Mail”, “The Financial Times” for the period from 2018-2022. In the course of the study, the following research methods were used:

- descriptive-analytical method;
- matching method;
- continuous sampling method;
- contextual method.

The theoretical basis of the research is the works of the following authors devoted to phraseology and linguistics Grigorieva L., Fakhrutdinova A., Zubkova O. (2019), and Andreeva Yu.A., Korneva I.G., Sahibullina K.A. (2019), Sitdikova F.B. (2019), Mubarakshina, A.A., & Abdrakhmanova A.A. (2019), Sabirova D.R., Solovyova E.G., Pomortseva N.P., Antonova S.P. (2019).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to investigate the peculiarities of idiomatic expressions in the British press, it is necessary to determine the main functions and features of the press. The main purpose of press is to convey certain information to the recipient in various forms – verbal, audio or visual. Moreover, the way of conveying information quite often becomes fundamental in defining the concept of mass media. The mass media have a great influence on the formation of the point of view of the whole society, form the norms of behavior of members of society. With the help of its “word”, the press influences the audience, helps people determine their assessment of certain events, etc. In this regard, it can be argued that the vocabulary of the press

should have such features that will help convince society of the point of view of the source of the media on a particular problem. In our opinion, a large number of different idiomatic expressions are used in the media, they make the text brighter, clearer and to some extent more convincing.

Undoubtedly, one of the most common types of idiomatic expressions found in the texts of the British press are *lexical idioms*, i.e. idioms that are combinations of individual words. For example, *at hand* – nearby, *play the game* – which means play by the rules, *to top it all* – the worst thing.

Morphological idiomatic expressions representing words whose parts have lost their semantic function are less common: *firsthand*.

Syntactic idioms, which are constructions whose meaning can be determined only from the context, are practically not used in the British press. Here is one example of using a syntactic idiom: *all the way* – from beginning to end, completely. Structurally, a wide variety of idioms can be observed in the texts of the British press:

- nominal idioms: *spot checks, blood on the floor, talking head*.
- verbal idioms: *slug out, give a lesson, act in concert, send somebody packing*.
- adverbial idioms: *at hand, all the way*.
- modal idioms: *at breakneck speed*.
- connective idiomatic expressions: *to top it all*.

The idiomatic expressions observed by us in the texts of the British press are characterized by extensive synonymous connections, for example, in two different articles there are idiomatic expressions denoting similar things but expressed in different forms. For example,

(1) *For example, the Commission, the Parliament and the European Council, where the states are represented, can **act in concert** to pursue actions under Article 7 of the EU Treaty, introduced by the Amsterdam Treaty in 1997 in order to avoid any backward step on democracy for any EU member state.* (“Hungary is no longer a democracy”, “New Statesman”).

*We’re part of the same media elite, we run in the same circles and we’re **playing the same game**.* (“Our news is dominated by people in expensive suits, shouting at each other”, “New Statesman”).

The idiomatic expression in the first example (1) “to act in concert” has the meaning “to act together”, which corresponds to the context of the sentence. The second idiomatic expression – “to play the same game” – has the same meaning, according to phraseological dictionaries and reference books. Although, judging by the context, the meaning here may be somewhat rethought.

(2) *The files are also thought to contain details about his spectacular kidnapping – perhaps even collusion between Israel and West Germany – **in pulling it off**.* (“German court blocks release of secret files on Nazi Holocaust mastermind Adolf Eichmann which would reveal how western spies knew where he fled after the war”, “Daily Mail”).

Consider another idiomatic expression (2) – “pull it off” – which has several completely different meanings from each other:

- 1) look good (about clothes),
- 2) tear off (get something valuable),
- 3) commit a crime,
- 4) achieve something, despite the difficulties.

The meaning of this idiomatic expression is determined only due to the context – commit a crime.

During the study of idioms in the texts of the British media, we observed a lot of deformed idioms. Idioms can be deformed in various ways. Based on the results of the study, we can say that one of the most popular ways of deforming idioms is to introduce an additional element into the composition of an idiomatic expression, which makes the idiom original and gives it additional aesthetics and value. Consider the following examples. In English, there is an idiomatic expression “*to make a splash*”, which is quite often used in the texts of the British media:

(3) *Buffett made a splash, but the biggest Heinz story is yet to come.* (“Buffett made a splash, but the biggest Heinz story is yet to come”, “New Statesman”).

In this sentence, the meaning of the idiom is to raise a fuss, to arouse interest.

This rather expressive idiomatic expression in one of the analyzed newspaper articles acquires even greater expression by adding a new element:

(4) *Buffet’s takeover has made a big splash, but one senses there are bigger Heinz stories to come.* (“Buffett made a splash, but the biggest Heinz story is yet to come”, “New Statesman”).

The adjective “big”, attached to one of the elements of the idiom, gives the whole idiomatic expression an enhanced expression and has a meaning in this case – to make a lot of noise.

If in the above example (4) the additional element only adds expression to the idiom, then in the following example the additional element almost completely changes the meaning of the idiom:

(5) *As if this wasn’t enough to excite the M&A markets, Buffet has been dropping noi-so-subtle hints that he’s planning some more big moves, telling CNBC that he was “ready for another elephant.”* (“Buffett made a splash, but the biggest Heinz story is yet to come”, “New Statesman”).

The idiom “drop a hint” means the following – to casually hint at something. The addition of the “not-so-subtle” element excludes the very nature of an “unintentional” hint at something, showing that the hint was intentional and unambiguous.

We have analyzed 200 idiomatic expressions selected by a continuous sampling method from the British media and based on the main function of the media, which consists in the open, public transmission of information, in the formation of public opinion, the vocabulary of mass media texts should be, on the one hand, objective and evidence-based, on the other hand, it should contain various figurative figures of speech, which can include idiomatic expressions. During the research, we found out that the British press uses a large number of idiomatic expressions of various types, i.e. different structural and semantic types. *Synonymy* of idioms is widely developed in journalism, which presents some difficulties in translating them into Russian. The same can be said about the ambiguity of some idiomatic expressions. It is necessary to emphasize such a feature of media idioms as the use of *deformed idioms*, i.e. such idiomatic expressions, which in the process of their use in the media acquire a unique figurative appearance.

4 SUMMARY

So, an idiom is a linguistic phenomenon that uses stable indecomposable phrases that are similar in composition to phraseological units. Idioms are reproducible, stable, low variable, consistent and have a single meaning and integral functionality of the language structure.

The general meaning of an idiom cannot be derived from the individual values of the elements of an idiomatic expression. Its meaning is almost always reinterpreted, and the meanings of the individual components of the utterance can be gradually forgotten.

From the point of view of the classification of idiomatic expressions, their differentiation by individual types may present some difficulties, since in some scientific works linguists correlate idioms with phraseological units of the language, which affects the uniformity of their classifications. Thus, the structural classification of idioms and phraseological units is of the same type: idioms are distinguished by their structure into idioms – free phrases, idioms with a compositional or predicative structure, idioms with the character of interjection, idioms of a comparative nature, single-vertex structures: consisting of a significant word and one or more official parts of speech and verb-postpositive idioms.

The function of idiomatic expression in the text is similar to the function of phraseology, in connection with which we can talk about such types of idiomatic expressions as nominative and nominative-communicative idioms.

Idioms, like phraseological units, can differ in their stylistic coloring, synonymic and antonymic connections, in the processes of polysemy and homonymy.

5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we may say that investigating the functioning of idiomatic expressions in the texts of the British media, it is necessary to understand the purpose of their use in journalism in general. The main task of the

media is not just to convey certain information to the recipient, but to communicate their point of view on the problem, focusing the recipient's attention on important details, in general, forming public opinion. As a result, the language of the media should be logical, evidence-based, informative, which does not exclude imagery and reinterpretation, on the other hand.

In this regard, it can be argued that the use of idiomatic expressions of various types and types is one of the main lexical features of the language of the media, and the playing of idiomatic expressions, their deformation is a fairly frequent situation.

REFERENCE LIST

- Andreyeva Y.A., Korneva I. G., Sakhbullina K. A. (2019). Values and anti-values in figurative phraseological units in the Russian and German languages. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, Vol. 7, is. 4, pp. 427-432.
- D'Arcais Giovanni B. Flores. *The Comprehension and Semantic Interpretation of Idioms*. Idioms: processing, structure, and interpretation. Edited by Christina Cacciari, Patrizia Tabossi. Hillsdale, N. J.: L.Erlbaum Associates, 1993, pp. 79–98.
- Grigoryeva L., Fakhrudinova A., Zubkova O. (2019). Reflection of religious worldview in Arabic, English and Russian phraseology. *Journal of Sociology and Social Anthropology*. Vol.10, is. 4, pp.203-208.
- Krysin L.P. (2008). *Tolkovy slovar' inoyazychnykh slov*. M.: Eksmo, 944 p.
- Langlots Andreas. (2006). *Idiomatic Creativity. A Cognitive-linguistic Model of Idiom-Representation and Idiom-Variation in English*. Human Cognitive Processing. John Benjamins Publishing Company: Amsterdam/Philadelphia. 326 p.
- Mubarakshina, A.A., & Abdrakhmanova, A.A. (2019). Theoretical bases of studying the vocabulary of sensory perception in the system of scientific research (on the material of Russian-speaking V. Nabokov's prose). *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(6), 93-97.
<https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2019.7620>
- Sabirova D.R, Solovyova E.G., Pomortseva N.P., Antonova S.P. (2019). Comprehension of the English national character in building professional linguistic culture. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*. Vol. 9, No. 3, pp. 101-106.
- Sitdikova F.B., Khisamova V.N., Mutigullina Z.A. (2019). Implicit negation in Tatar phraseology. *Journal of Sociology and Social Anthropology*. 10(4), pp. 175-179. DOI: 10.31901/24566764.2019/10.04.308